

Improving Student Interest in Science through Innovative Teaching Strategies

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ABSTRACT

This action research addresses science disengagement among Grade 7 students in Sri Lanka. The study focused on one persistently disengaged student at a specific international school who exhibited low participation, incomplete assignments, and negative attitudes toward science despite better performance in other subjects. Using Kurt Lewin's Action Research Model, two intervention rounds incorporated hands-on experiments, digital simulations, inquiry-based learning, gamification, and project-based activities. Data were collected through classroom observations, semi-structured interviews with the student, class teacher, and parent, alongside analysis of science notebooks and reflective journals. Results demonstrated significant improvements in classroom engagement, task completion, scientific vocabulary use, collaborative behaviour, and confidence. The student progressed from avoidance to active participation, successfully presenting a science model and demonstrating leadership in group activities. Findings confirm that differentiated, interactive, and student-centred strategies effectively transform attitudes toward science, particularly for learners who perceive the subject as irrelevant or difficult. Recommendations include embedding hands-on activities, technology-enhanced learning, and inquiry-based methods into regular science instruction to sustain motivation and foster deeper conceptual understanding among all students.

Keywords: *Innovative teaching strategies, student engagement, science education, action research, active learning*